

Studies on the Interactions of Biological Metal Ions with some Sulphonamide Drugs. Part-I. Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Sulphapyridine, Sulphadiazine and Sulphathiazole

G. N. MUKHERJEE*, (Mrs.) S. BASU and T. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 30 August 1993

Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric studies on the complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine and sulphathiazole (LH) provided evidence of formation of binary complexes ML^+ and ML_2 , together with ternary hydroxo complexes of the types, $ML(OH)$, $ML_2(OH)^-$ and $ML_2(OH)_2^{2-}$. Formation constants of the complexes were determined at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$). Stability of the complexes were found to be in the order : $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$ for all the three ligands, and in the order : sulphapyridine > sulphathiazole > sulphadiazine with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} , whereas in the order : sulphadiazine > sulphapyridine > sulphathiazole with Cu^{II} . Stability of the complexes were correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligands.

Sulphanilamide (1) and its derivatives, popularly known as sulpha-drugs¹ are commonly used for the treatment of various infectious diseases, viz. meningitis, sepsis, pneumonia etc. caused by gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Like most of the reactions occurring in the biological systems, the action of a drug also requires, apart from the reactant substrates, the presence of specific enzymes as catalysts, most of which require one or other of the biological metal ions². Due to complexity of the enzyme structures, it is rather difficult to elucidate the specific roles played by the metal ions in the enzymic processes. However, related studies with model systems have often yielded very useful results, although the metal binding properties of the functional groups in the proteins may not be the same as those in the model compounds. With a view to throw some light upon the interactions of sulpha-drugs with the metalloenzymes, a systematic equilibrium study on the interactions of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with some commonly used drugs, viz. sulphapyridine (SPH, 2), sulphadiazine (SDH, 3) and sulphathiazole (STH, 4) have been undertaken and the results are presented here.

Results and Discussions

All the three ligands sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine and sulphathiazole in their protonated forms titrate as biprotic acids (LH_2^+) and offer two well separated buffer regions, due to successive deprotonation of $\overset{+}{N}H_3$ and $-SO_2NH-$ moieties. This

is evident from a comparison of the successive pK^H values of these ligands with the corresponding values (2.00 and 10.05) of sulphanilamide (1). A structurally related compound, 2-benzene sulphoamidopyridine (5) titrates as a monoprotic acid ($pK^H = 9.10$) even in the presence of equimolar

amount of added acid. This pK^H value is close to that of the $-SO_2NH-$ moiety³. This suggests the non-involvement of the hetero N or S atoms in the proton-ligand equilibria of these ligands.

Complex formation of M^{2+} ions with these ligands takes place above pH 3, where the ligands predominately exist in their neutral (LH) forms. Therefore, the NH_2 group in the *para*-position to the $-SO_2NH-$ group in these ligands, is not involved in metal-ligand complexation equilibria.

Complex formation of Cu^{II} with these ligands is accompanied by change of colour of the solution. 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : sulphapyridine mixtures assume reddish brown colour (λ_{max} 625 nm at pH 5.75). Absorbance of the solutions increases with rise of pH, but the λ_{max} value remains unaltered at 625 nm (Fig. 1). Similar mixtures of Cu^{II} with sulphadiazine and sulphathiazole assume violet colouration, with λ_{max} values at 620 and 615 nm respectively, and the λ_{max} values do not shift with change of pH of the solutions.

This suggests similar type of ligand atoms around Cu^{II} in its complexes with all these ligands. The absorption band near 450 nm corresponds to charge transfer transition.

Composition of the complexes formed in the solutions were determined spectrophotometrically at pH 5.75 following Job's method of continuous variation⁴. Such study indicated the formation of 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : ligand complexes in all the three systems.

Buffer regions corresponding to the metal-ligand complexation equilibria with all these M^{2+} ions are found to be close to those corresponding to

Fig. 1. Electronic spectral curves of 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : ligand mixtures at different pH : (a) Cu^{II} -sulphapyridine, (b) Cu^{II} -sulphadiazine and (c) Cu^{II} -sulphathiazole; [Cu^{II}] = 3×10^{-4} M, [ligand] = 1.5×10^{-3} M, $I = 0.1$ M ($NaNO_3$) in 50%(v/v) aqueous ethanol medium, path-length = 1 cm.

the hydrolytic equilibria of M^{2+} (aq) ions (Fig. 2). Therefore, the formation of hydroxo species of the types, $M(OH)^+$ and $M(OH)_2$ have also been taken into consideration in calculating the formation constants of metal-ligand complexes. Though there are scopes for the formation of 2 : 1 metal : ligand complexes with the sulphadiazine (3) and sulphathiazole (4) ligands, but 2 : 1 M^{2+} : ligand mixtures on pH-metric titration do not give any new buffer region other than that observed due to the hydrolytic equilibria of M^{2+} (aq) ions. Such 2 : 1 M^{2+} : ligand solutions turn turbid at the pH values corresponding

to the precipitation of $M(OH)_2$ under the experimental conditions. In the 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 5 M^{2+} : ligand mixtures, the formation of ternary metal

Fig. 2. pH-titration curves of Cu^{II} -sulphapyridine (LH) system : (1) 0.01 M HNO_3 , (2) (1) + 0.001 M $Co(NO_3)_2$, (3) (1) + 0.001 M $Ni(NO_3)_2$, (4) (1) + 0.001 M $Cu(NO_3)_2$, (5) (1) + 0.001 M $Zn(NO_3)_2$, (6) (1) + 0.01 M sulphapyridine in the form of (LH_2^+) , (7) (6) + 0.001 M $Co(NO_3)_2$, (8) (6) + 0.001 M $Ni(NO_3)_2$, (9) (6) + 0.001 M $Cu(NO_3)_2$, (10) (6) + 0.001 M $Zn(NO_3)_2$; initial volume of each solution 25 ml, titrant 0.1 M NaOH, $I = 0.1$ M ($NaNO_3$) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol.

ligand hydroxo complexes of the types, $ML(OH)$, $ML_2(OH)$, $ML_2(OH)_2$ etc. can not however be ruled out. So the species LH_2^+ , LH , L^- , M^{2+} , ML^+ , ML_2 , $ML(OH)$, $ML_2(OH)^-$ and $ML_2(OH)_2^{2-}$ have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria on calculating the formation constants using the SCOGS⁵⁻⁷ programme. The computer output gives the overall formation constants of the complexes as well as the complex distribution curves, which are useful in elucidating the complexation equilibria. Representative distribution curves for the three Cu^{2+} -ligand systems are shown in Figs. 3–5. Similar nature of the distribution profiles of all the metal-ligand systems studied, indicates the formation of similar types of complexes. Distribution profiles (Figs. 3–5) of M^{2+} , LH , ML^+ and ML_2 species indicate the formation of ML^+ and ML_2 complexes according to equilibria (1a) and (2a).

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -sulphapyridine (LH) system : (1) LH_2^+ , (2) LH , (3) L^- , (4) Cu^{2+} , (5) $Cu(OH)^+$, (6) $Cu(OH)_2$, (7) $Cu(L)^+$, (8) $Cu(L)_2$, (9) $Cu(L)(OH)$, (10) $Cu(L)_2(OH)^-$, (11) $Cu(L)_2(OH)_2^{2-}$.

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -sulphadiazine (LH) system : (1) LH_2^+ , (2) LH , (3) L^- , (4) Cu^{2+} , (5) $Cu(L)^+$, (6) $Cu(L)_2$, (7) $Cu(L)_2(OH)^-$, (8) $Cu(L)_2(OH)_2^{2-}$.

Fig. 5. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II} -sulphathiazole (LH) system : (1) LH_2^+ , (2) LH , (3) L^- , (4) Cu^{2+} , (5) $Cu(OH)^+$, (6) $Cu(OH)_2$, (7) $Cu(L)^+$, (8) $Cu(L)_2$, (9) $Cu(L)(OH)$, (10) $Cu(L)_2(OH)^-$, (11) $Cu(L)_2(OH)_2^{2-}$.

$$K_{ML}^M = \frac{[ML^+]}{[M^{2+}][L^-]} \quad (1b)$$

$$K_{ML_2}^{ML} = \frac{[ML_2]}{[ML^+][L^-]} \quad (2b)$$

The observed λ_{max} values of 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : LH mixtures at pH values corresponding to the maximum formation of CuL₂ complexes (Fig. 1) suggest tetragonally distorted octahedral [Cu(O)₂(N)₂(H₂O)₂] geometry⁸ for Cu^{II} in these complexes. Thus the L⁻ ligand ions derived from all the three ligands, viz. sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine or sulphathiazole (LH), coordinate Cu^{II} as (O, N) bidentate ligands. These ligands can provide such coordination using one of the two oxygen atoms of the -SO₂NH- group and a nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic ring systems. Such coordination (6 and 7) by a sulphanil oxygen atom labilises the sulphonamide proton, which is released during complexation (eqm. 1a and 2a). The resulting complexes are further stabilised by resonance (6) ↔ (7).

Two L⁻ ligands ions in the ML₂ complexes occupy four coordination sites around the octahedral M²⁺ (aq) ions, which obviously take up two molecules of the solvent (H₂O or C₂H₅OH) as additional ligands to attain the octahedral or distorted octahedral geometry (8). Closeness of the λ_{max} values of the Cu^{II}-ligand mixtures at pH values corresponding to the maximum formation of CuL₂(H₂O)₂ complexes (8) with sulphadiazine

(X = N) and sulphathiazole (X = S) rules out the possibility of coordination by the hetero-sulphur atom instead of the hetero-nitrogen atom of the

latter ligand. Shifting of the ν_{as} and ν_s ir bands due of -SO₂N- group of the ligands around 1 355–1 322 and 1 170–1 140 cm⁻¹ respectively, to lower wavenumbers in the ir spectra of Cu^{II} complexes of the type CuL₂·2H₂O, also suggests this mode of coordination by all the three ligands^{9,10}. Electronic spectra of these CuL₂·2H₂O complexes also correspond to distorted octahedral Cu(O)₂(N)₂(H₂O)₂ geometry around Cu^{II}.

Species distribution curves (Figs. 3–5) show the appearance of three hydroxo complexes, ML(OH), ML₂(OH)⁻, ML₂(OH)₂²⁻ above pH 5.6 with concomitant disappearance of the ML₂⁺ and ML₂ complexes. Obviously, these hydroxo complexes are formed through deprotonation of coordinated water molecules in the binary ML⁺ and ML₂ complexes according to,

$$K_{ML(H_2O)_4}^H = \frac{[ML(OH)(H_2O)_3][H^+]}{[ML(H_2O)_4^+]} \quad (4b)$$

$$K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^H = \frac{[ML_2(OH)(H_2O)^-][H^+]}{[ML_2(H_2O)_2]} \quad (5b)$$

$$K_{ML_2(OH)(H_2O)}^H = \frac{[ML_2(OH)_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[ML_2(OH)(H_2O)^-]} \quad (6b)$$

The deprotonation constants, $K_{ML(H_2O)_4}^H$, $K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^H$ and $K_{ML_2(OH)(H_2O)}^H$ were calculated from the computer refined values of the formation constants K_{ML}^M , $K_{ML_2}^M$ and the overall formation constants (β^H) using the relations.

$$\log K_{ML(H_2O)_4}^H = \log \beta_{(M+LH+H_2O)}^{2H} - \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{LH}^H \quad (7)$$

$$\log K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^H = \log \beta_{(M+2LH+H_2O)}^{3H} - \log K_{ML_2}^M - 2 \log K_{LH}^H \quad (8)$$

$$\log K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^{2H} = \log \beta_{(M+2LH+2H_2O)}^{4H} - \log K_{ML_2}^M - 2 \log K_{LH}^H \quad (9)$$

$$\log K_{ML_2(OH)(H_2O)}^H = \log K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^{2H} - \log K_{ML_2(H_2O)_2}^H \quad (10)$$

The pK^H values of coordinated water molecules in the $M(L)(H_2O)_4$ and $ML_2(H_2O)_2$ complexes are found to be much lower than the pK_w of water (Table 1). Such increased acidity of coordinated water molecules arises from the enhancement of electronegativity of M^{2+} ions in these complexes (8) due to delocalisation of the metal $d\pi$ -electrons over to the LUMO of the extended aromatic π -system of the ligands. The charge transfer bands near 450 nm in the electronic absorption spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes (Fig. 1) give further evidence to this proposition. pK^H values of coordinated water molecules in the $Cu(L)(H_2O)_4^+$, $Cu(L)_2(H_2O)_2$ and $Cu(L)_2(OH)(H_2O)$ complexes are found to be quite close to those found in analogous systems^{3,11,12}. This provides an indirect evidence to the validity of the proposed mode of bonding of the ligands in these complexes.

K^H values of coordinated water molecules of $M(L)^+$ and $M(L)_2$ complexes derived from all the three ligands SPH, SDH and STH, are found to increase with the stability constants of these complexes. An interesting correlation diagram (Fig. 6)

shows the validity of Irving-Williams order : $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$, in the stability constants of $M(L)(H_2O)_4^+$ complexes, and almost an inverse order is found in the pK^H values of these complexes.

Fig. 6. $pK_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^H$ vs $\log K_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^M$ correlation diagram : (O, Δ , \square) $\log K_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^M$ values, (\bullet , \blacktriangle , \blacksquare) $pK_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^H$ values for M^{2+} -SPH, M^{2+} -SDH and M^{2+} -STH complexes ($M^{2+} = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) respectively.

Similar correlation is also observed in the case of $M(L)_2(H_2O)_4$ complexes of these ligands. Slight reversal in the pK^H values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes probably arises from partial oxidation of the Co^{II} complexes at higher pH values of the solutions.

Experimental

The ligands, sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine and sulphathiazole (all Aldrich) were directly used after checking their purity by elemental analysis, m. p., uv and ir spectra. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol¹³.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND M^{2+} -LIGAND CONSTANTS* WITH SULPHAPYRIDIN (SPH), SULPHADIAZINE (SDH) AND SULPHATHIAZOLE (STH) AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS-ETHANOL MEDIUM AND IONIC STRENGTH $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$)

Ligand (LH)	Metal(II)	SPH	SDH	STH
$pK_{LH_2}^H$	—	1.94	2.96	1.79
pK_{LH}^H	—	9.60	7.38	7.89
$\log K_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^M$	Co	3.83	2.61	3.44
	Ni	3.96	3.14	3.57
	Cu	5.66	6.97	4.50
	Zn	4.39	2.76	3.60
$\log K_{M(L)_2(H_2O)_2}^M$	Co	7.53	5.09	6.51
	Ni	7.48	5.60	6.97
	Cu	10.62	12.65	8.39
	Zn	7.84	5.60	6.53
$pK_{M(L)(H_2O)_4}^H$	Co	7.76	7.95	8.26
	Ni	8.18	8.94	7.75
	Cu	5.53	7.31	6.59
	Zn	7.05	9.36	8.00
$pK_{M(L)_2(H_2O)_2}^H$	Co	6.00	6.70	6.14
	Ni	5.32	6.61	6.33
	Cu	5.14	6.04	5.75
	Zn	7.85	7.17	5.99
$pK_{M(L)_2(OH)(H_2O)}^H$	Co	11.29	9.34	8.14
	Ni	10.88	8.91	8.15
	Cu	9.34	8.56	7.50
	Zn	11.45	9.85	9.00

*Limits of error in the constants : ± 0.05 in log units.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				λ_{max} (EtOH) nm
	Cu	N	S	Loss at 105°	
$Cu(SP)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	10.79	13.95	10.59	5.89	450
	(10.65)	14.09	10.74	6.04)	625
$Cu(SD)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	10.32	18.56	10.51	5.86	445
	(10.62)	18.73	10.70	6.02)	620
$Cu(ST)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	10.26	13.64	20.89	5.77	450
	(10.45)	13.82	21.05	5.92)	615
$Cu(SP)_2$	10.94	14.50	11.02		
	(11.34)	14.99	11.42)		
$Cu(SD)_2$	11.17	19.65	11.21		
	(11.30)	19.92	11.38)		
$Cu(ST)_2$	11.23	14.82	22.17		
	(11.11)	14.68	22.37)		

Metal nitrate solutions were standardised by ion-exchange separation, combined with acid-base and complexometric EDTA titrations¹⁴. Carbonate-free NaOH solution¹⁵ was used as the titrant.

pH measurements were made with a Systronics μ -361 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) employing a special glass electrode in conjunction with SCE. The following solutions were prepared for the pH-metric study : (i) 0.01 M HNO₃, (ii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.001–0.002 M M(NO₃)₂, (iii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.005 – 0.01 M ligands in the forms of LH₂⁺ and (iv) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.005–0.01 M LH₂⁺ + 0.0005–0.002 M M(NO₃)₂. Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium. Required amount of NaNO₃ was placed in each solution to maintain the ionic strength constant at $I = 0.1M$. The solutions were allowed to attain the equilibrium at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated). All the solutions (i–iv) were pH-metrically titrated with a standard carbonate free 0.1M NaOH solution prepared in the same solvent medium and maintained at the experimental temperature. A representative set of pH-titration curves for the Cu^{II}-sulphapyridine system are presented in Fig. 2.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were evaluated with the aid of the computer programme SCOGS⁵⁻⁷, run on a PC-XT computer system. Preliminary estimates of some of the constants supplied to the computer as input data, were evaluated by analysing the pH titration curves (Fig. 2) according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁶. Computer refined values of the formation constants are stated in Table 1.

Preparation of Cu(L)₂.2H₂O complexes : Ethanolic solutions of the ligands (sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine or sulphathiazole; 0.2 mmol) were treated with aqueous solution of copper nitrate (0.1 mmol) and pH of the solutions were adjusted to 5–6

by adding dilute NaOH solution. The resulting solutions were evaporated on a hot water-bath. The precipitated complexes were collected by filtration, washed with 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol, recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, air-dried and analysed (Table 2). These CuL₂.2H₂O complexes on dehydration at 105° lost two molecules of water. Analytical data (Table 2) of the dehydrated products correspond to Cu(L)₂.

References

1. P. G. STEEHER, "The Merck Index of Chemicals and Drugs", Merck and Co., Rahway, 1960, p. 992.
2. A. L. LEHNINGER, "Biochemistry", Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, 1978, Chap. 26, p. 732.
3. G. N. MUKHERJEE and P. K. CHAKRABORTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1935, **24**, 841.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. Paris*, 1928, **9**, 113.
5. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397.
6. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1970, **18**, 653.
7. I. G. SAYCE and V. S. SHARMA, 1972, **19**, 831.
8. H. SIGEL and B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 325.
9. L. J. BELLAMI, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, New York, 1980, Vol. 2, p. 226.
10. N. N. GHOSH and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 517.
11. A. E. MARTELL, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **17**, 129.
12. G. N. MUKHERJEE and S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 941.
13. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1968, p.167.
14. I. M. KOLTHOFF, B. B. SANDELL, E. J. MEEHAN and A. BRUCKENSTEIN, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", Macmillan, London, 1967, Chap. 41.
15. G. SCHWARZENBACH and W. BIEDERMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 331.
16. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

